

Guidelines for operating Vaisala CL61

WG3 subgroup:

Automatic lidars and ceilometers (ALC)

Version: 08 May 2025

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1 OBJECTIVES

This document describes guidelines for operating a Vaisala CL61 ceilometer. The guidelines follow recommendations by the EU COST action PROBE for automatic lidars and ceilometers (ALC).

Vaisala CL61 is a high-performance light detection and ranging (LiDAR) instrument with depolarization capable of unattended operation 24/7 in all weather conditions. The depolarization measurement capability enables clear liquid/solid differentiation for particles and clouds, providing ready-to-use information for atmospheric characterization.

The CL61 is utilizing parallel (PPOL) and cross (XPOL) polarized attenuated backscatter profiles to report the volume linear depolarization (DEPOL) ratio profile. The DEPOL profile is XPOL divided by PPOL. In addition to above mentioned profiles the CL61 also reports total attenuated backscatter profile (ABS) which is XPOL plus PPOL profiles, cloud base altitude and sky condition in octas.

Due to the high amount of data the output is provided in netCDF format. The CL61 requires Ethernet connection and (S)FTP server for file transfer from the unit to the data collection system. The procedure is described in the CL61 manuals.

2 FIRMWARE

Vaisala is constantly improving the ALC firmware versions. It is important to always follow the latest recommendations on firmware updates.

How to check the firmware generation?

The firmware generation is listed in the netCDF file under the global attribute “history”. As an example, this is how it looks inside the file:

```
// global attributes:
:title = "CL61D CL61-arya-3 with Depolarization";
:institution = "Vaisala";
:source = "Arya-3";
:conventions = "CF-1.8";
:schema_version = "1.3";
:sw_version = "1.2.7";
:history = ;
:comment = "HEL Testfield";
:unit = "m";
:instrument_serial_number = "M12334567";
:overlap_function_provided = 1S; // short
:overlap_is_corrected = 1S; // short
:file_temporal_span_in_minutes = 5.0; // double
:profile_interval_in_seconds = 60; // int
```

In this example the firmware version in use is 1.2.7.

The firmware version is also available via SSH connection (maintenance or data ethernet port using PUTTY or similar, see CL61 User's Guide) connection with the following commands, where the firmware version (1.2.7 in this example) is visible in the beginning of the “SW version”:

```
>Level 2
```

```
2> dump
```

CL61 Ceilometer CL61

Product serial: T2710847

Product revision: A

Manufacturing date: 2021-07-06T12:15:29Z

SW version: 1.2.7

CLC611 Device Controller Board:

Item serial: T22302

Item revision: F

A firmware update is done with the *Vaisala Field Application* tool. Instruction details are provided in the in CL61 User's Guide.

3 RECOMMENDED SETTINGS

To harmonise the ALC profile observations across the network, E-PROFILE is recommending a temporal resolution of 30 s. The vertical resolution is 4.8 m, which cannot be changed for the CL61. Also, it is recommended to switch on the sky condition algorithm which provides additional products of cloud cover (only available with firmware 1.1.0 onwards).

The CL61 measures XPOL and PPOL alternatingly every 0.2 s and averaged those internally to 5 s profiles, so the CL61 determines the attenuated backscatter (ABS) and polarization profiles (PPOL and XPOL) at a 5 s interval. The depolarization ratio (DEPOL) profile is calculated at 10 s intervals from the 10 s averages of PPOL and XPOL, respectively. The internal averaging and file size can be adjusted inside the CL61. The maximum averaging is 2 minutes inside CL61. The backscatter profiles and the depolarization ratio profile have separate averaging schemes. Below we list the default settings and maximum resolution settings for all profiles available (Table 1). Note that multiples of 5 s profiles are required when changing the averaging interval for attenuated backscatter and 10 s for linear depolarization ratio. More information is provided in CL61 User's Guide. The following table 1 shows examples of measurement averaging schemes.

Table 1: Default, recommended, and maximum temporal resolution settings for the CL61.

Parameter	Value
DEFAULT (v 1.1 onwards)	
5 profiles with 1-minute averaging □ 5-minute file	
algo.l1averaging.interval	12
algo.l1averaging.depolinterval	12
reporting.profile.interval	12
reporting.livefile.profilesperfile	5
RECOMMENDED (PROBE and E-Profile)	
10 profiles with 30-second averaging □ 5-minute file	
algo.l1averaging.interval	6
algo.l1averaging.depolinterval	6
reporting.profile.interval	6
reporting.livefile.profilesperfile	10
MAXIMUM RESOLUTION	
12 profiles with 5s averaging, 12 DEPOL profiles with 10s rolling average □ 1-minute file	
algo.l1averaging.interval	1
algo.liaveraging.depolinterval	2
reporting.profile.interval	1
reporting.livefile.profilesperfile	12

Parameter explanations are:

<i>algo.l1averaging.interval</i>	Averaging interval for ABS, XPOL, and PPOL in L1 / Number of 5 s profiles averaged in each x-polarization (XPOL), p-polarization (PPOL), and attenuated backscatter profile (ABS).
<i>algo.l1averaging.depolinterval</i>	Averaging interval for depol in L1 / Number of 5 s profiles averaged in each depolarization profile
<i>reporting.profile.interval</i>	Interval for reporting to write out profiles
<i>reporting.livefile.profilesperfile</i>	Number of profiles that are written in each .nc file

4 KNOWN ISSUES

- Vaisala has identified a **transmitter power decrease** in early units (with firmware 1.0, units delivered in 2021 and end of 2024). To assess the stability of the laser power of a CL61, firmware v1.1.10 or higher is needed. Vaisala is recommending a firmware update to v1.2.7 (or higher) so that proper transmitter power measurements and status information are recorded. With these *housekeeping data*, the instrument operator and/or the coordinated sensor network can monitor the transmitter power automatically.
Note: Not all CL61's suffer from this premature transmitter power decrease. Therefore, in case the instrument reports decreased power of the transmitter the customer should contact Vaisala helpdesk for the support. Vaisala is replacing affected transmitters under warranty.
- Vaisala has identified an issue on CL61 **window sealing** for a few units. Affected windows have been replaced under warranty. The issues can be fixed for units installed at customer sites and all user's will be contacted by Vaisala (by end of 2023) to add additional sealing for their existing units. If instrument operators observe leakage from the window, they are advised to contact the Vaisala Helpdesk and so that the window can be replaced under warranty.
- It was identified that in fog conditions the lowest range gates show NaN values in profiles. It is an algorithm bug and it is estimated to be fixed in the next firmware release which is estimated to be available at the end of 06/2025. It is also related to instrument sensitivity and therefore not all of them suffer from this and some might suffer more than others. A simple restart of the CL61 might fix it.
- It was identified that there is a small increase of the backscattered signal around 130m. This local maximum can be detected with hood measurements. However, for typical conditions in the boundary layer this effect can be ignored.

5 OPEN ISSUES

- Laser heater causing alternating strong signals for about 2 min in the first range gates (<30 m?)
- An artifact in the backscatter signal around 80m has been observed for one CL61 sensor, probably related to the overlap, while the blind zone is supposed to be up to 40m.

APPENDIXES AND OTHER INFO

Appendix A – CL61 firmware log

Latest documentation (User's Guide, Installation Guide, upcoming firmware releases, Data sheet and other available documentation related to CL61) is available online: <https://docs.vaisala.com>

The latest firmware v.1.2.7 package is available from here:

<https://vaisala.my.salesforce.com/sfc/p/D0000000IZdo/a/2p000000BUXT/qJLk6lf4YMj5Md0.kufldcUjONEuiEfof56aBRX5E0>

NOTE: New upcoming firmware releases will be shared via <https://docs.vaisala.com>